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VIRTUAL REALITY AS AN EDUCATIONAL TOOL IN THE TREATMENT OF CHRONIC PAIN: PROTOCOL FOR A FEASIBILITY STUDY

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Introduction

Chronic pain significantly impacts quality of life and requires comprehensive management strategies. Traditional pain education programs are beneficial but often require significant and prolonged patient engagement. Virtual reality (VR) offers a novel approach by creating immersive environments that may enhance the effectiveness of pain education. This protocol outlines a feasibility study to investigate the use of a Virtual Reality Pain Education Program (VRPEP) for people living with chronic pain (PwCP).

Aim of the investigation

The primary aim will be to evaluate the feasibility of delivering a VRPEP for PwCP. The secondary aim will be to explore the pre-to-post-test changes in outcome measures relating to pain self-efficacy and fear avoidance behaviours as proof of concept for a future larger scale investigation.

Methods

This study will be conducted as a single-arm feasibility study using a pre-test post-test design. 50 PwCP will engage in a 6-week VRPEP, focusing on the neurophysiology of pain, pain modulation techniques, cognitive-behavioural strategies and guided virtual exercises.

Results

Primary outcome measures will include the feasibility, acceptability and safety of the VRPEP, including recruitment, retention, intervention adherence and attrition rates. Secondary outcomes will include efficacy measures relating to changes in pain intensity, quality of life and physical, emotional and cognitive functioning.

Conclusions

Results will establish the feasibility, acceptability and safety of a VRPEP in the treatment of chronic pain, informing a future randomised control trial.

Ethical approval: Ethics will be sought from University College Dublin's Human Research Ethics Board and ethics boards of relevant clinical sites.

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